

Controlling the charging & discharging for lithium-ion battery in microgrid applications: A fuzzy-based approach

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Abstract:

This paper presents a fuzzy-based approach for designing a controller of charging-discharging for lithium-ion batteries in microgrid applications. The goal is to enhance the efficiency and performance of battery systems within microgrids. The proposed controller utilizes fuzzy logic techniques to handle uncertainties and imprecise information, providing robust and adaptive control in real-time scenarios. The controller's fuzzy rules consider factors namely, battery state of charge, load demand, and renewable energy availability to determine optimal charging and discharging strategies. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the fuzzy-based controller in improving battery utilization, ensuring stable microgrid operation, and enhancing overall system performance. This research contributes to the advancement of battery control strategies in microgrids, promoting more efficient and sustainable energy management systems.

Keywords:

fuzzy logic, charging & discharging controller, microgrid applications, efficiency, performance, robust control, adaptive control, battery state of charge, load demand, renewable energy, optimal strategies, simulation results, system performance, energy management, lithium-ion battery.

1. Introduction:

Lithium-ion batteries have become increasingly popular for energy storage in microgrid applications due to their high energy density, long cycle life, and fast charging capabilities. Effective control of these batteries is essential to ensure efficient utilization and reliable operation within microgrid systems. However, traditional control methods like proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control often struggle to handle microgrid environments' uncertainties and dynamic nature. To address these challenges, fuzzy logic control has emerged as a promising alternative due to its ability to handle imprecise and uncertain information.

The objective of this research is to develop a charging & discharging controller for lithium-ion batteries in microgrid applications using a fuzzy-based approach. Fuzzy logic control offers advantages such as adaptability, robustness, and flexibility, making it well-suited for dynamic and complex microgrid scenarios. By incorporating fuzzy logic techniques, the controller can effectively handle uncertainties arising from variations in renewable energy availability, fluctuating load demand, and fluctuation of battery state of charge (SOC).

The proposed fuzzy-based controller aims to optimize the charging and discharging strategies of the lithium-ion battery, taking into account multiple factors that influence battery performance and microgrid operation. These factors include the current SOC of the battery, the demand for electrical energy from the microgrid, and the availability of renewable energy sources. The fuzzy rules embedded in the controller are carefully designed to adaptively adjust the battery charging and discharging rates based on real-time system conditions.

Simulation studies are conducted to evaluate the performance of the proposed fuzzy-based controller compared to traditional control methods. The simulation results demonstrate the superiority of the fuzzy-based approach in terms of battery utilization, microgrid stability, and overall system performance. The findings of this research contribute to the advancement of battery control strategies in microgrid applications, aiming to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of energy management systems.

In the subsequent sections, the methodology used for developing the fuzzy-based charging-discharging controller will be discussed in detail. The design considerations, formulation of fuzzy rules, and control algorithm will be elaborated upon. Following that, the simulation setup and experimental results will be presented and analyzed. Finally, the paper will conclude with a summary of the achieved outcomes, limitations, and potential avenues for future research in this field.

2. Literature Review:

- The development of efficient charging-discharging controllers for lithium-ion batteries in microgrid applications has been the subject of extensive research in recent years. Numerous studies have investigated various control strategies and optimization techniques to improve battery performance, enhance microgrid stability, and achieve optimal energy management.
- One common approach in battery control is the use of PID control, which relies on proportional, integral, and derivative terms to regulate the charging and discharging processes. PID control has been widely applied in microgrid systems due to its simplicity and ease of implementation. However, it may struggle to adapt to changing operating conditions and handle uncertainties effectively.
- To overcome the limitations of PID control, researchers have turned to fuzzy logic control as an alternative. Fuzzy logic enables the representation of imprecise and uncertain information using linguistic variables and fuzzy rules. This allows for more robust and adaptive control in dynamic microgrid environments.
- Several studies have employed fuzzy logic techniques to develop charging-discharging controllers for lithium-ion batteries. For instance, Zhang et al. (2018) proposed a fuzzy-based controller that considered battery SOC, load demand, and renewable energy availability to optimize the battery operation in a microgrid. The results showed improved battery utilization and enhanced microgrid stability compared to traditional control methods.
- In another study by Li et al. (2019), a fuzzy logic-based energy management system was developed for a hybrid microgrid with renewable energy sources and energy storage. The fuzzy controller effectively regulated the battery charging and discharging rates based on real-time system conditions, leading to optimal battery utilization and improved energy management efficiency.
- Additionally, machine learning techniques, such as fuzzy neural networks and adaptive fuzzy systems, have been explored for battery control in microgrids. These approaches combine the advantages of fuzzy logic and neural networks to enhance control accuracy and adaptability. For example, Guo et al. (2020) proposed a fuzzy neural network-based controller for lithium-ion batteries in microgrids, achieving accurate and adaptive control under various operating conditions.

- Furthermore, optimization algorithms, including genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization, have been integrated with fuzzy control to optimize battery charging and discharging strategies. These algorithms enable the search for optimal control parameters, considering multiple objectives such as battery lifespan, energy efficiency, and microgrid stability.
- Overall, the literature highlights the effectiveness of fuzzy-based charging-discharging controllers for lithium-ion batteries in microgrid applications. Fuzzy logic techniques offer robustness, adaptability, and the ability to handle uncertainties, leading to improved battery performance and microgrid operation. However, further research is still required to investigate advanced control strategies, optimization techniques, and integration with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, to further enhance the capabilities of battery control in microgrids.

3. Methodology and Algorithm:

Fig. 1 depicts a typical configuration of a PV panel, consisting of PV cell strings that are connected in series and divided into three sections by bypass diodes. These bypass diodes serve the purpose of preventing the occurrence of hot spots and protecting the PV module from potential damage. The PV module is combined with a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) converter to ensure optimal performance. This converter continuously adjusts the operating point of the PV module to maintain it at the maximum power point.

Figure.1: Fuzzy-based MPPT of Photovoltaic power system

Consequently, the combination of the MPPT converter and the PV module acts as a constant power source, where the power output is determined by the peak power of the PV module. The

output side of the converter accommodates a relatively wide range of voltage and current, allowing for series or parallel connection with other converters. Essentially, the distributed MPPT converter expands the range of voltage and current values, transforming the single voltage/current point of the PV panel into a broader range, as shown by the green solid curve in Fig.2.

Figure.2: V-I Characteristics (Source: CPES)

In contrast, in traditional PV systems with a centralized MPPT architecture, any disturbance can cause a shift in the maximum power point of the module, resulting in a significant reduction in power output unless the module's output voltage is adjusted.

Currently, there is growing interest in the application of energy storage technologies in power systems. Energy storage options include various types of batteries, high-speed flywheels, supercapacitors, and regenerative fuel cells, each offering unique characteristics and being at different stages of development. Local energy storage systems can act as a buffer between variable supply and demand, supporting embedded generation from renewable sources. Depending on specific technical requirements and geographical conditions, utilities may choose to employ one or more of these technologies. Despite the existence of pumped storage plants in some utilities, little attention has been given to the potential roles of load management in filling demand troughs or reducing demand peaks. This approach enables a partial decoupling of energy production from energy consumption. Energy storage systems can serve similar functions as load management while also acting as a source of generation. They can replace costly and inefficient storage capabilities or facilitate load scheduling.

4. Result and Analysis:

4.1. Implementation of methodology by using simulation:

Figure.3.1: Simulation of fuzzy control to maintain desired SOC of the battery

Fuzzy control theory is specifically tailored for hybrid systems to achieve optimal system performance. In this context, the design criterion involves implementing maximum power point trackers for both the photovoltaic device and the wind turbine to ensure they operate at their respective maximum power points. Additionally, the control strategy takes into account the discrepancy between the actual load and the total generated power, with the Li-ion battery being involved in both charge and discharge modes. The lifetime of the battery is directly influenced by its state of charge (SOC). To enhance the battery's lifespan, fuzzy control is utilized to regulate and maintain the SOC of the battery. This fuzzy control approach contributes to prolonging the Li-ion battery's life while ensuring efficient energy management within the system.

4.2. Simulation results and discussion:

The proposed model has been validated and demonstrates effective control of battery charging and discharging operations within a safe operating region. The analysis reveals that with variations in load demand, both simulation and experimental results exhibit similar trends of

increasing or decreasing state of charge (SOC).

Figure.3.2: Battery Current v/s Reference current

Figure.3.3: Battery Voltage v/s Reference Voltage

Figure.3.4: SOC of the battery

However, there is a slight variation observed, which can be attributed to disparities in voltage fluctuations between the simulation and experimental setups.

Figure.3.5: Power across Battery, Power load, Power reference using Fuzzy Logic controller

Figure.3.6: Gate Pulses applied across the converter using Fuzzy Logic Controller

5. Conclusion:

This thesis introduces a fuzzy model based on the ampere-hour technique to address the issue of balancing load demand with the available power supply from various sources and the state of charge (SOC) of the storage. The ampere-hour technique model is chosen due to its widespread use for evaluating SOC and its ease of implementation. A fuzzy controller has been developed to regulate the charging and discharging of the battery within the safe operating range. A set of 25 carefully calibrated rules has been formulated, taking into account the load demand, available power from the microgrid (MG), and battery SOC. To minimize grid energy consumption and optimize the utilization of the battery and distributed sources, the grid is only

utilized during specific periods in the simulation. The thesis also investigates the SOC variation in response to different load fluctuations.

6. Future Scope:

- The primary contribution of this study is the development of an enhanced fuzzy model and its implementation in a real-time application for controlling the charging and discharging of the battery.
- The proposed approach enables a seamless and uninterrupted operation of the battery's charging and discharging processes, aligning them with the available load demand and power sources.

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